

Multigrid analysis implementation in SDAP 1.7

Version 1.0

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The latest SDAP code for UnixTM and Linux is available from the repository of the project -- see <http://sequoia-dap.sourceforge.net> .

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1. SDAP code concepts and architecture

1.1. Purpose

SDAP initially meant "SEQUOIA Data Assimilation Platform". It can also be read recursively as "SDAP Data Assimilation Platform".

The purpose of SDAP is to provide a flexible platform to carry out multivariate assimilation of geophysical data in a numerical model, and interpret the results. The program is multi-geometry (finite differences or finite elements), multi-algebra (plug-in analysis kernels), multi-model (simple standardized interface). The program supports reduced-order data assimilation methods, as well as Ensemble assimilation approaches such as the Ensemble Kalman Filter.

1.2. Code

The SDAP code is a modern versioned code focused primarily on Ensemble data assimilation, but much more besides:

- Open Source licensing (GPL/CeCill)
- Written in Fortran-95 with some Fortran-2003 and -2008 extensions (in particular regarding genericity, use of pointers, objects, methods, derived types and classes); compiles under Intel, GNU and Cray programming environments
- Requires BLAS, LAPACK, NetCDF and an MPI library
- Fully modular
- Programmable from safe user space; foolproof separation between user-side, SDAP-side and kernel-side
- Can work on structured model grids (finite difference) as well as with finite elements / finite volume model grids via a system of generalized grid. Its standardized interface with numerical models allows it to couple with virtually any model.

The latest SDAP code for UnixTM and Linux is available from the repository of the project -- see <http://sequoia-dap.sourceforge.net> .

1.3. Library

The SDAP-side code resides in a main library (`SDAP-lib`), which includes some essential components, among which the following:

- EVENT (general secretary: registers, reports, handles all exceptions)
- GEO (geometry) – including full spherical distances and structured/unstructured grids
- ODB (Observational DataBase)
- UNCERT (Modelling of Uncertainties) and EMU (Ensemble Modelling of Uncertainties)
- FIELD (3-D fields)
- SIOS (Samples I/O System)
- OLA (Off-Line Analysis) libraries

- ASEYA (Interprocess communication and synchronization) – interfaced with MPI
- KDTREE (K-d tree fast search in 2-D and 3-D Cartesian spaces)
- PACK (handling of packed/sparse matrices)
- NCLIB (NetCDF i/o)
- SPRUCE agents: `_init`, `_data`, `_datapert`, `_integrate`, `_harvest`, `_analyze`.

The components interface if needed with the user-side code and with the analysis kernels in a formalized way, whenever possible adopting object-oriented rules.

1.4. Configurations

SDAP comes with a selection of configurations in `etc/conf/` and matching SDAP-side, kernel-side and user-side software components in `components/`. Each configuration is built from the common SDAP libraries and specific user-side code. In that way, the existing applications in each configuration can be dynamically modified from the user side without running the risk of tampering with the static SDAP libraries. Similarly, new configurations and their applications can be added.

Configurations can be installed using `make newconfig`, which also installs the appropriate configuration file and ancillary files. The configuration file `sdap.conf` registers all software components that are needed to build the applications in the current configuration, including the analysis kernel, as well as other parameters (compiler, libraries) which can be adjusted by the user.

1.5. Applications

All applications for a configuration are normally compiled with `make`.

For each application, one basic parameter is the execution context (`sdap_event_mod :: context`), which sets the type of processing and user interaction mode:

<code>context</code>	<i>Processing type</i>	<i>User interaction</i>
0	Full scalar run	Possible
1	Scalar run Ensemble-aware, no members list file (<code>mlist</code>)	Possible
2	Scalar run Ensemble-aware, <code>mlist</code>	Possible
3	Parallel assimilation run in SEQUOIA flavor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “SDAP calls model”: SDAP handles MPI communicators and message passing, member identity and execution directory • No domain decomposition possible 	No
4	Parallel assimilation run in SPRUCE flavor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Model calls SDAP”: model handles MPI communicators and message passing, member identity and execution directory • Domain decomposition (double parallelization) possible 	No

When carrying out Ensemble analysis/forecasting cycles, the SDAP model interface comes in two environment flavors (`sdap_event_mod :: flavor`):

- In the SEQUOIA flavor (`context=3` above), in-memory coupling with the model is implemented (one single executable per member); SDAP sets the rules and takes care of the MPI communicators. In that flavor, the model libraries must be made first, then the SDAP configuration.
- In the SPRUCE flavor (`context=4` above), most communication occurs via NetCDF files; domain decomposition is allowed; the model takes charge of the MPI communicators. In that flavor, the SDAP libraries and modules must be made first, then the model (with the appropriate SDAP hooks), then possibly some of the tools.

In addition to assimilation proper, the main SDAP library provides the environment needed to build a variety of scalar and/or Ensemble-aware tools, e.g. for post-processing, diagnostics and user-defined tasks, some of them provided with the distribution, such as `olax` on SDAP-side, and `scrumcat` and `atlas` on user-side. These tools are usually built under `context=0, 1` or `2`.

The tables `sdap_event_mod` :: `runmode_list`, `runmode_flavor`, `runmode_context` register all known applications that can be built from the current distribution.

1.6. Plug-in analysis kernels

The analysis kernel *algebrae* reside in specific kernel-side libraries separate from the main SDAP library. This allows the kernels to be interchangeable by changing the kernel name in `sdap.conf`.

BELUGA is a full-rank kernel solved in the dual space, used in a 4D localized implementation of the Ensemble Kalman Filter using MPI for scheduling of parallel runs in an Ensemble. It is a local analysis kernel in the sense that it solves a local inversion problem within an “influence bubble” around each model gridpoint, using a suboptimal set of local predictors. The BELUGA kernel is described in detail in De Mey (2014).

Some other analysis kernels are experimental or deprecated (available on request).

1.7. Run-time parameters before the multigrid extensions

The behavior of applications can be changed at runtime by means of parameter files. The parameter definitions follow the Fortran NAMELIST format and rules. In general, either default or “reasonable” parameter files, if available, are installed at configuration time. The parameter files may contain SDAP-side, kernel-side and/or user-side parameter definitions.

The SDAP-side NAMELISTs are:

- `&run_attributes: label, aim`
- `&debug: debug_msglev, debug_grid_node, debug_grid_node_coord`
- `&time_sequence: ttmin, ntimes, tint, if_smoother, dtpast`
- `&julian_calendar: julian_time_unit, julian_ref_year, julian_time_unit_out, julian_ref_year_out`
- `&obs: nobs_max, nsets, fname, dformat, status, srate, nsel, redun, pformat, if_noiseless, ampmax, qcrange, xrange, yrange, zrange, trange, unacc_type, avproxrad, datapert_randgen_seed`

- `&fileinfo: x_var, y_var, z_var, t_var, yo_var, err_var, yo_type`
- `&scrum: if_pert_yo, iterations, if_remav_yf, if_remav_yo, if_remav_dy, if_use_pers, tol1, tol2`

The kernel-side NAMELISTs are:

- `&kernel: kernel_if_analysis, kernel_if_equil, kernel_if_prewhiten, kernel_if_con, kernel_if_metrics, kernel_msglev`

Some frequent user-side NAMELISTs are:

- `&obs_uncert: EO_SDEV0_SSH, EO_SDEV0_SST, EO_SDEV0_CHLA, EO_SDEV0_DEFAULT, ROX0, ROY0, ROZ0, ROT0`
- `&prior_uncert: RIX0, RIY0, RIZ0, RIT0, LFUNCNUM0, RLX0, RLY0`
- Tool-specific NAMELISTs
- Model-specific NAMELISTs
- Ensemble input NAMELISTs.

2. Multigrid implementation

2.1. Overall scope of the new developments

In its release 1.7¹, SDAP was modified in order to be able to handle multiple simultaneous model and estimation grids, as well as multigrid prior ECM and multigrid state and control vectors, while remaining compatible with double parallelization across Ensemble members and domain decomposition (see example MPI instances diagram in Fig. 1).

Agents	Model integration?	Multigrid?	Single process • MPI comms																							
MPI instance		Yes	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Member		Yes	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	4	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	4
Subdomains of grid # 1		Yes, grid # 1	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Subdomains of grid # 2		Yes, grid # 2	4	5		4	5		4	5		4	5		4	5		4	5		4	5		4	5	
1. sdap_init	Yes	Yes	•			•			•			•			•			•			•					
2. sdap_data		Yes	•																							
3. sdap_datapert		Yes	•			•			•			•			•			•			•					
4. sdap_integrate	Yes	Yes (AGRIF)	•			•			•			•			•			•			•					
5. sdap_harvest		Yes (MG-SIOS)	•																							
6. sdap_analyze		Yes (MG-EMU)	•			•			•			•			•			•			•					

Figure 1: SDAP/SPRUCE time/instances diagram for an example with 4 members and 2 grids. The multigrid additions in SDAP 1.7 are indicated in yellow. It is assumed that grid # 1 (e.g., the “parent”) has 3 subdomains allocated by the domain-decomposition scheme, and grid # 2 (e.g., the “child”) has 2 subdomains – of course this works also when the parent and the child have the same number of subdomains. In addition, the subdomains in one MPI instance do not have to be geographically related across grids.

These developments were undertaken to support the Copernicus Marine Service Evolution project MULTICAST, in an effort to address, in a parent-child 1-way and 2-way nested dynamical model configuration, the assessment of the forecasting skill as well as the formulation of the multigrid control vector for data assimilation.

2.2. Development process

All in all, development took more than a year to the author. To give an order of magnitude of the effort undertaken to that end, the number of lines of code in version 1.6 of the SDAP main library was 34612, which has risen to 41853 in version 1.7, corresponding to an increase of 20.9% (obviously not counting rewritten parts of code).

The developments occurred in most parts of the code:

- Class-based handling of dynamically-allocated grids within a “multigrid”.
- Development of the multigrid versions of the GEO, FIELD, SIOS, EMU, ODB and OLA library components, to name the most critical ones.
- Multigrid definitions of prior and observational uncertainties (the so-called **B** and **R** ECMs), in particular introducing cross-grid error covariances and cross-grid localization.

¹ <https://sourceforge.net/p/sequoia-dap/code/HEAD/tree/branches/1.7/>

- Multigrid extensions of the suboptimal procedures – in particular a fully programmable multigrid influence to control the influence of innovation on one grid onto others.
- Multigrid versions of the `olax` and `scrumcat` tools.
- Multigrid versions of all standalone drivers (SEQUOIA, SCRUMCAT) and of the SPRUCE agents.

In the following, we focus on the multigrid implementation of the analysis (although the new developments have concerned all parts of the code). We will remain SDAP-side and kernel-side, only giving general indications for the user-side.

2.3. Changes in run-time parameters

The SDAP-side NAMELISTs have been modified as follows: (**bold = new in multigrid version**)

- `&run_attributes: label, aim, n_grids`
- `&debug: debug_msglev, debug_grid_number, debug_grid_node, debug_grid_node_coord`
- `&time_sequence: ttmin, ntimes, tint, if_smoother, dtpast`
- `&julian_calendar: julian_time_unit, julian_ref_year, julian_time_unit_out, julian_ref_year_out`
- `&obs: nobs_max, nsets, fname, dformat, status, srate, nsel, redun, pformat, if_noiseless, ampmax, qcrange, xrange, yrange, zrange, trange, unacc_type, avproxy_rad, datapert_randgen_seed, grid_switch`
- `&fileinfo: x_var, y_var, z_var, t_var, yo_var, err_var, yo_type`
- `&scrum: if_pert_yo, iterations, if_remav_yf, if_remav_yo, if_remav_dy, if_use_pers, tol1, tol2`

The kernel-side NAMELISTs are unchanged:

- `&kernel: kernel_if_analysis, kernel_if_equil, kernel_if_prewhiten, kernel_if_con, kernel_if_metrics, kernel_msglev`

Some user-side NAMELISTs have been modified as follows: (**bold = new in multigrid version**)

- `&prior_uncert: RIX0, RIY0, RIZ0, RIT0, XGRID_INFL0, LFUNCNUM0, RLX0, RLY0`

2.4. Principles and usage of multigrid analysis

2.4.1 Grid instances

Principles:

We introduce the grid class via a derived type (`sdap_grid_struct` in module `sdap_geo_mod`). All grid-dependent objects (i.e. most objects in the code) are now

instantiated via dynamic allocation. The code must be able to accommodate as many grids as needed, regardless of any geometric overlap between grids (but overlaps and interpolation between grids are handled internally). The multigrid capability is fully compatible with both Ensemble operation and domain decomposition (double parallelization) – subdomains can span several grids and do not have to overlap geometrically.

Usage:

- *SDAP-side:*
 - New NAMELIST parameters are introduced. See **Section 1.7**.
 - The code handles all principles above internally in a manner that is transparent to the user.
- *User-side:*
 - The `u_ingrid()` routine is now responsible for setting all grids in the multigrid.

2.4.2 *Multigrid samples and covariances*

Principles:

The Ensemble library becomes fully multigrid (each member sample is multigrid). Hence all state-space covariances are multigrid. But representers (covariances between state space and data space) may or may not be multigrid depending on how we choose to model the cross-grid influence of observations in a specific run (see *Subsection 2.3.4*).

Usage:

- *User-side:*
 - If the configuration implies to read samples from file, then this has to be repeated for each grid. Therefore, for instance, the Ensemble input NAMELISTs will now contain grid-dependent Ensemble sample file names and NetCDF variable definitions.

2.4.3 *Grid-dependent observations*

Principles:

The observational database is global and unique, allowing each local analysis to be ultimately carried out within a multigrid vicinity (multigrid influence bubble). Each observation can be activated/deactivated on each grid, and can have a grid-dependent error model (error standard deviation + error correlation radii in all dimensions).

Usage:

- *SDAP-side:*
 - All observations can be activated/deactivated per grid, by means of the diagonal of boolean `&obs:grid_switch` (self-influence).
- *User-side:*
 - Observations can have specific error models per grid, as set by `u_uncert_obs_set()` (e.g. through `&prior_uncert`).

2.4.4 Cross-grid influence of observations

Principles:

We want the influence of observations to be fully programmable *quantitatively* across grids. For instance the observations on grid_B may be allowed to appear in the grid_A analysis, but not the other way around. But we also want this to be fine-tuned *qualitatively*, both in terms of the sizes of influence bubbles, which can vary from grid to grid, and in the way the suboptimal predictor selection algorithm is made to select observations from other grids.

Usage:

- *SDAP-side:*
 - Cross-grid influence matrix: one boolean per pair of grids, per direction grid_A → grid_B : these are the off-diagonal terms of `&obs:grid_switch`
- *User-side:*
 - Suboptimal predictor selection: cross-grid influence factor² set by `u_uncert_prior_set_influence()` (e.g. through `&prior_uncert:XGRID_INFL0`)
 - Specific influence bubble definition on each grid set by `u_uncert_prior_set_influence()` (e.g. through `&prior_uncert:RIX0,RIY0,RIZ0,RIT0`)

2.4.5 Cross-grid localization

Principle:

We follow rules similar to those for cross-grid influence, but with the possibility to choose independent, specific radii for localization. Also the localization function is defined independently on each grid.

Please note that for a local inversion on a grid, even if that inversion contains observations from other grids resulting from suboptimal cross-grid predictor selection (see *Subsection 2.3.4*), the localization (function and radii) is uniquely defined from the localization parameters *of the current grid*³.

Usage:

- *SDAP-side:*
 - Localization uses the cross-grid influence matrix `&obs:grid_switch`
- *User-side:*
 - Specific localization definition on each grid set by `u_uncert_prior_set_localization()` (e.g. through `&prior_uncert:LFUNCNUM0,RLX0,RLY0`)

² This is still an unstable feature. The stable algorithm will be further documented in a future revision of this document. For now, the interested reader can consult the code itself.

³ The introduction of a cross-grid localization factor is an option which is being considered.

2.4.6 *Analysis algebra*

Principles:

We use the exact same algebra as in the single-grid case, therefore the reader is referred to De Mey (2014) for the math. Only the high-level debug output is modified to report on the grid number we are processing.

Usage:

- Kernel-side:
 - No changes except for high-level debug output.

3. Acknowledgments

Support of the author by Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) is acknowledged. Some developments were supported by the Copernicus Marine Service Evolution project MULTICAST. We are grateful to our colleague Vassilis Vervatis (U. Athens) for his great help in testing the new developments in the streamlining/debugging phase in 2023-24.

4. References

De Mey, P., 2014: The SEQUOIA manual. Available in the current branch under `etc/doc/`.